

Infrared Spectroscopic Studies of EOM from Cambay Basin

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The infrared spectroscopy has been used for characterisation of EOM, asphaltenes and crude oils of the Cambay basin. The functional groups of EOM, asphaltene and crude oil were characterised and extinction ratios at maximum wavenumbers of the respective groups were calculated. On the basis of these data, the type of EOM, its evolution path and original organic matter of Cambay basin have been identified.

EOM is considered as complex mixture of high molecular weight hydrocarbons and non-hydrocarbons which can be separated into saturate, aromatic, resin and asphaltene fractions. Three types of hydrocarbons are present in EOM, viz. paraffinic, naphthenic and aromatic. NSO compounds contains heterocyclic atoms such as sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen. The chemical properties of all these compounds vary systematically with increasing molecular weights. The chemical nature of many of the EOM constituents depends upon original source organic compounds and depositional environments^{1,2}. The data on EOM of Cambay basin have clearly indicated that source organics consist of various molecules having similar structure and constitute a characteristic structural groups. However, the data are still lacking on chemical nature and properties of various EOM constituents of Cambay basin.

The literature reveal that infrared spectroscopy has been used in structural elucidation of coals, humic compounds etc., for the characterisation of the EOM and evolution path of kerogen³⁻⁸. No such type of the studies have been carried out for the EOM of Cambay basin. Hence in the present investigation, an attempt has been made to characterise the type of EOM, its evolution path and source organics of Cambay basin using infrared spectroscopic technique.

Results and Discussion

The assignment of infrared absorption bands for EOM, asphaltene and crude oils of Cambay basin are presented in Table 1. The extinction values of each absorption band is calculated by applying baseline method⁹,

$$E_v = \log P_o / P$$

where E_v is the extinction at a particular wavenumber, P_o the distance from zero transmitted line to the baseline for a absorption peak at a particular wavenumber, and p the distance from zero transmitted line to absorption maximum for a absorption peak at a particular wavenumber. The calculated extinction values at assigned wavenumber for EOM, asphaltenes and crude oils are used for characterising the different genetic types for determining their evolution paths and the type of organic matter deposited initially in the sediment (Figs. 1 and 2).

Genetic type of EOM, asphaltene and crude oils : EOM in source rocks may be present as (i) syngenetic or autochthonous and (ii) migratory or allochthonous. The content and the nature of syngenetic EOM are useful indicators of quality and thermal maturity of source organics. Presence of migratory type of EOM in source rocks is a significant indicator of release and redistribution and occurrence of primary migration process that leads

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to oil accumulations¹⁰. The areal frequency occurrence of migratory EOM in sedimentary basins has been related to distribution of oil in a basin¹¹.

TABLE 1—ASSIGNMENT OF IR SPECTRAL BANDS FOR EOM, ASPHALTENE AND CRUDE OIL OF CAMBAY BASIN

ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	Assignment
3 430	Hydrogen bonded CH stretching with a possible N-H contribution
2 962–2953	C-H stretching from CH ₃ (2 962, 2 872) and CH ₂ (2 926, 2 856)
1 710	C=O stretching due to carbonyl (aldehyde and ketone) and carboxyl (acid and ester)
1 630	Dominated by (C.....C) stretching of aromatic rings unsaturated olefinic bonds and polyaromatic structures C=O stretching of quinones bridged to acidic hydroxyl
1 460–1 440	Partly due to deformation vibrations of OCH ₃ and CH ₂
1 380–1 375	Ring stretching vibrations due to CH ₃ only
1 225–1 215	Skeletal stretching deformation of C–C–CH
1 400–1 040	A wide band resulted due to C–O stretching and CH deformation
930–700	Weak band related to various aromatic CH (bending out-of-plane)
850–750	Weak absorption due to C–H bending vibrations of olefinic and aromatic structures
760–750	C–H bending vibrations of substituted aromatic ring
722	Rocking vibrations of (CH ₂) _n where n ≥ 4, C–S vibrations of sulphide

Fig. 1. Relation between E_{1710}/E_{1450} and degree of bitumenisation (β) of EOM from Cambay basin.

Fig. 2. Relation between degree of bitumenisation (β) and total organic carbon content (%) for onland Cambay basin.

The infrared spectra of some of the EOM asphaltene and crude oils of Cambay basin show that a wide band with a maximum around 1 710 cm⁻¹ is observed in most of the spectra of EOM and asphaltene, while in the case of crude oils, a very small band or no band appears at 1 710 cm⁻¹. A very intense band at 1 450–1 460 cm⁻¹ is also observed. The band at 1 710 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the various groups, viz. aldehyde, ketone, acid and esters. During evolution of organic matter, oxygen atoms from carbonyl and carboxyl groups progressively eliminate as water and carbon dioxide from diagenetic EOM which contains large amounts of NSO compounds. In natural process this is characterised by marked decrease of oxygen content C=O band at 1 710 cm⁻¹ progressively disappears. On the contrary, band at 1 410 cm⁻¹ characteristic of methylene group, increases due to the formation of hydrocarbons during evolution of sedimentary organic matter.

For the quantitative determination by infrared spectrum, a ratio E_{1710}/E_{1450} can be used to characterise EOM. The relation of E_{1710}/E_{1450} of EOM with degree of bitumenisation (β) of the rock samples of Cambay basin are shown in Fig. 1. Uspensky¹² reported a relationship between β and total organic content (TOC) which shows that a ratio of E_{1710}/E_{1450} at 0.5 is the demarcation of autochthonous (> 0.5) and allochthonous (< 0.5)⁵⁻⁷. The line drawn at 0.5 indicates the autochthonous and allochthonous EOM which is in agreement with those obtained by Uspensky's curve^{12,13} (Fig. 2). However, it is

observed that EOM from Santhal-1 (Sa-1 to Sa-5) and SDAE (SD-1 to SD-5) wells deviate from these findings and characterised as autochthonous. The plot of E_{1700}/E_{1450} -VS resulted that these EOM are of allochthonous type. This is due to the fact that the nature and maturity of organic matter play a significant role to generate EOM. Hence their composition can be known by infrared spectroscopy and classified on the basis of E_{1700}/E_{1450} ratio.

The infrared spectrum of EOM also shows that an intense band at $1\ 355\text{--}1\ 365\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ is due to the symmetric C-CH₃ band. The ratio $E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ can be used to measure the branching of isohydrocarbons and applied to characterise EOM. The branched hydrocarbons migrate much easier and on the other hand the starting sample influences the quantity of isoprenoid. The relation between $E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ and E_{1710}/E_{1450} is demonstrated in Fig. 3. The demarcation line can be drawn at 1.2 for $E_{1355-1465}/E_{1450}$ at 0.5 for E_{1710}/E_{1470} to characterise EOM^{6,14}. The absorbance band located at $1\ 600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ for EOM of Cambay basin is attributed partly to conjugated C=C bond and partly to carbonyl C=O group. The ratio E_{1600}/E_{1450} denotes the aromatic content and it is cross plotted with E_{1710}/E_{1450} for EOM in Fig. 4. It separates out autochthonous EOM from allochthonous at 0.5. The type of starting material should also be taken into account since humic substances generate much more aromatic structure than the sapropel types.

Thus the following indices are developed to characterise EOM : (i) E_{1710}/E_{1450} —characteristic of carbonyl group of EOM, (ii) E_{1600}/E_{1450} —proportional to aromatic content of EOM, and (iii) $E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ —proportional to branching of isohydrocarbons of EOM. All these extinction ratios for EOM, asphaltene and crude oils of Cambay basins are calculated. These results for crude oils and asphaltene are shown in Figs. 3–6.

Thus E_{1710}/E_{1450} ratio proved to be characteristic for the classification of genetic types of EOM from Cambay basin (Figs. 1, 3, 4). It is observed that all crude oils have this ratio < 0.5 and are classified as allochthonous type. The EOM which has this ratio < 0.5 , are classified as allochthonous are considered to be compositionally very similar to crude oil (Figs. 3–4). About 50% EOM of Cambay basin

Fig. 3. Relation between E_{1710}/E_{1450} and $E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ of EOM and crude oils from Cambay basin.

Fig. 4. Relation between E_{1710}/E_{1450} and $E_{1600-1365}/E_{1450}$ of EOM and crude oils from Cambay basin.

are classified as migratory in nature, which proves that Cambay basin is oil producing zone.

An attempt has also been made to investigate the role of asphaltene played in oil generation by studying the variations in its structure in relation to EOM. The same extinction ratios used for characterisation of EOM have been utilised for asphaltene separated from EOM crude oil of Cambay basin.

The values are presented in Tables 1 and 2 and plotted in Figs. 5, 6. It is observed that in most of the cases the nature of EOM and asphaltene remained the same, i.e. asphaltene carries same imprint of autochthonous or allochthonous nature of EOM but asphaltenes are more aromatic than EOM. The latter fact is clearly reflected in Fig. 6. This has also been confirmed by Behar *et al.*¹⁵, who indicated that 40–50% carbon atoms in petroleum asphaltene are aromatic.

Evolution path of organic matter : It has already been established that kerogen is the precursor of EOM. Crude oils are migrated from EOM and form commercial pool. Tissot and Welte⁸ and Behar *et al.*¹⁵ reported that asphaltene is considered as a

Fig. 5. Relation between E_{1710}/E_{1450} and $E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ of asphaltene separated from EOM and crude oils of Cambay basin.

Fig. 6. Relation between E_{1710}/E_{1450} and E_{1600}/E_{1450} of asphaltene separated from EOM and crude oil from Cambay basin.

kerogen moiety which can be easily studied in detail in place of kerogen. Hence all asphaltenes (are considered as equivalent to kerogen) and EOM of Cambay basin are studied by infrared spectroscopy to understand evolution path of organic matter for the generation of hydrocarbons.

TABLE 2—GC AND PYROLYSIS STUDIES OF EOM*

Well	Total organic		β	S	HI	OI	%				HC ppm	Range n-Alkene	Maxi. nC	nC_{31}/nC_{19}	$nC_{21} + nC_{22}/nC_{28} + nC_{29}$
	C%	EOM %					Sat	Ar	As	R					
JO-6 Jotana-5	2.66	0.13	4.90	11.29	387.5	—	30.35	7.45	7.45	54.75	491	C ₁₄ -C ₂₆	nC ₁₈ , nC ₂₇	0.46	0.51
SO-7 Sobhasan-57	6.08	0.56	9.26	9.70	121	29	9.57	19.13	43.57	27.73	1616	C ₁₅ -C ₃₄	nC ₂₁	0.16	1.47
SO-8 Sobhasan-57	13.08	1.27	9.74	64.97	470	13	4.37	8.27	64.73	22.67	1602	C ₁₅ -C ₃₄	nC ₂₇	—	—
WO-2 Wadu-1	5.34	0.20	3.70	17.34	316	—	—	—	—	—	—	C ₁₅ -C ₃₄	nC ₂₆	1.20	0.92
SO-1 Sobhasan-66	5.98	0.47	7.84	11.28	175	26	4.95	7.11	28.56	59.38	565	C ₁₃ -C ₃₂	—	—	—
SO-2 Sobhasan 66	8.39	0.52	6.18	17.91	197	—	4.94	15.38	28.33	51.35	1053	C ₁₃ -C ₃₂	—	—	—
SO-3 Sobhasan 66	7.14	0.64	9.00	15.64	194	17	14.87	10.64	39.14	35.35	1641	C ₁₃ -C ₃₂	nC ₂₉	1.25	0.76
SO-4 Sobhasan 66	5.83	0.54	9.19	14.09	221	23	7.17	17.02	27.19	48.62	1297	C ₁₃ -C ₃₂	—	—	—
LY-10 Lynch-3	3.11	0.19	6.14	1.03	30	16	9.16	14.79	15.79	60.26	457	C ₁₆ -C ₃₀	nC ₂₀	—	2.97
LY-11 Lynch-3	1.35	0.11	8.47	1.05	68.1	—	20.74	16.49	39.36	23.41	426	C ₁₄ -C ₃₄	nC ₂₁	0.30	2.41
LY-12 Lynch-3	1.73	0.17	9.65	0.58	33	21	21.98	18.36	13.82	45.82	674	C ₁₇ -C ₃₁	nC ₂₂	0.93	2.71
LY-13 Lynch-3	1.39	0.07	5.05	0.58	26	20	10.04	24.20	24.20	41.56	240	C ₁₇ -C ₃₁	nC ₂₂	0.93	2.71
LY-14 Lynch-3	1.44	0.06	3.83	0.78	34	—	7.47	6.58	25.32	60.63	349	C ₁₇ -C ₃₁	nC ₂₂	0.93	2.71

*C = Total organic carbon; β = degree of bitumenisation; S = hydrocarbon (mg/g) of rock; HI = hydrogen index; OI = oxygen index; Sat = saturate; Ar = aromatic; As = asphaltene; R = resin.

During evolution path, a useful general variation in the complex structure of EOM can be obtained using the following absorption ratio particularly in comparative sense¹⁵ : E_{1710}/E_{1450} related to carbonyl group, (ii) E_{1600}/E_{1450} related to aromatic content, (iii) $E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ related to isoalkanes, and (iv) E_{750}/E_{720} related to aliphatic chain. The evolution path of organic matter can be studied only for autochthonous EOM^{10,14}. With this view, in the present investigation, the evolution studies of EOM from Jotana-5, 10 and Lynch-2, 3 and 4 wells which show mainly autochthonous, have been discussed. The extinction ratios are calculated. It is observed that during diagenesis due to increase of temperature, first the carbonyl and carboxyl groups of asphaltene are broken and heteroatoms especially oxygen are partly escaped as volatile products, viz. H₂O, CO₂ etc. The studies of infrared spectra of asphaltene of Cambay basin at different intervals of depth show that there is a decrease in the intensity of characteristic C=O band at 1710 cm⁻¹ with the increase of depths, which may be due to the evolution of the kerogen. As further the evolution increases, the second stage of kerogen degradation (catagenesis) begins and the aliphatic content proportionally decreases and hence correspondingly the intensity of the absorption aliphatic band also decreases. However, there is an increase in the intensity of aromatic content increasing with depth (temperature). Hence the extinction ratio of E_{1710}/E_{1450} in asphaltene (kerogen) decreases with the increase of depth. Similarly, it has been observed that the other extinction ratios, viz. concerning with CH₂, CH₃ groups and aromatic content also vary with the depth. When the kerogen moiety becoming more and more condensed the ratio E_{1600}/E_{1450} increases regularly^{16,17}. These observations can be further correlated with the Van Krevelen diagram⁸ for the H/C and O/C ratios of organic matter. The oxygen content due to the breaking of carbonyl, carboxyl group (removal of C=O group) decreases and carbon content increases due to the formation of aromatic C-H during evolution of organic matter. Hence the ratio O/C decreases with increase in depth (temperature). This may remain low or even relatively higher due to elimination of hydrogen and carbon.

Similarly, it is observed that in the evolution of EOM, extinction ratio E_{1710}/E_{1450} decreases and

$E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ increases due to generation of hydrocarbons and E_{1600}/E_{1450} ratio is relatively increased. The kerogen is believed as a precursor of EOM, and during evolution kerogen is losing the hydrocarbons. This is clearly reflected in the comparative evolution path of asphaltene (kerogen) and EOM of Cambay basin. The extinction ratio of $E_{1355-1365}/E_{1450}$ for asphaltene decreases, while it increases for EOM with depth. The aliphatic chain during the main phase of oil generation (MPOG) in EOM in terms of E_{750}/E_{720} ratio is obtained, however, it is not observed in asphaltene.

The evolution path for asphaltene and EOM can be summarised as follows for asphaltene (kerogen) : (i) removal of COOH and CO group, (ii) removal of aliphatic chain and (iii) formation of aromatic C-H; and for EOM, (i) removal of COOH and CO group, (ii) increase in aliphatic chain and (iii) relatively increase in aromatic.

The above studies of evolution path for Jotana-5, 10 and Lynch-2, 3, 4 establish the fact that hydrocarbon generation process has been taken place in Cambay basin.

Identification of the type of organic matter for Cambay basin by ir spectroscopy : It has been reported by several workers^{1,5,8,16,17} that the ir spectra of the organic matter of types I and II, which contain mainly aliphatic chain and aromatic nuclei, give the intense bands due to CH₃ and CH₂ groups in the region 2962–2872 and 2926–2856 cm⁻¹ respectively. Similarly, type III organic matter which originates mainly from terrestrial plants, shows bands of condensed polyaromatic nuclei and oxygenated functional groups around 900–700 and 1710 cm⁻¹, respectively. An attempt has been made to identify the type of original organic matter by ir spectroscopy, from which EOM of Cambay basin is generated.

The type of organic matter from the wells of Cambay basin as identified by GC and pyrolysis studies, is given in Tables 2 and 3 along with the average extinction ratios at characteristic wavenumbers : area covered at 2930–2880 (various aliphatic C-H group), 900–700 cm⁻¹ (various aromatic C-H group) and 1710 cm⁻¹ (various oxygenated functional group). The following ratios are calculated :

$$(1) \text{ Ha} = \frac{E_{2920}}{E_{2920} + E_{2880}}$$

A fraction of H-atom attached to aromatic carbon

$$(2) \text{ Hme} = \frac{E_{1365}}{E_{2920}}$$

Total no. of H-atom present in CH₃ group

$$(3) \frac{(\text{Aliph. grs.})}{(\text{Arom. grs.})} = \frac{E_{2920} + E_{2880}}{E_{900} - 700}$$

$$(4) \frac{(\text{Aliph. grs.})}{(\text{Oxy. grs.})} = \frac{E_{2920} + E_{2880}}{E_{1710}}$$

$$(5) \frac{(\text{Arom. grs.})}{(\text{Oxy. grs.})} = \frac{E_{900} - 700}{E_{1710}}$$

It can be observed from Table 3, that type II organic matter contains more aliphatic groups (Hme) compared to type III. The aromatic content in type III is relatively higher than type II. It can be further observed that the values of Ha increase as aliphatic aromatic decrease for Lynch well. This criteria is mostly applicable for type III organic matter confirming that Cambay basin has mainly type III organic matter.

Preparation of EOM samples :

The pulverised and homogenised 66 rock samples from Cambay basin were extracted with double-distilled chloroform until no fluorescence was observed in the chloroform extract. The chloroform was distilled and EOM separated.

Preparation of crude oil and asphaltene fraction from crude oil and EOM : Crude oil samples collected from 15 different fields of Cambay basin were used for infrared studies. The crude oil contained whole range of hydrocarbons (mostly C₁-C₃₅). The residue of the crude oil (C₁₅) corresponded to the EOM of the sediment. The reported method¹⁸ was used to separate residue from crude oil. The oil sample (~100 g) was kept under infrared lamp for 6 h and the semisolid residue was taken for subsequent analysis. The residue (~2 g) was treated with distilled petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) (~200 ml) and refluxed overnight. It was then filtered and treated with distilled petroleum ether (~200 ml) and again filtered to collect asphaltene.

TABLE 3—AVERAGE EXTINCTION RATIOS AT CHARACTERISTIC WAVE-NUMBERS OF EOM OF CAMBAY BASIN FOR IDENTIFICATION OF ITS TYPE OF ORGANIC MATTER

Lab. code no.	Well no.	Ha	Hme	Aliph. grs. Arom. grs.	Aliph. grs. Oxy. grs.	Arom. grs. Oxy. grs.
<i>Type II organic matter :</i>						
JO-6	Jotana-5	0.63	0.29	3.36	9.49	2.96
SO-7	Sobhasan-57	0.64	0.29	5.62	10.61	1.85
SO-8	Sobhasan-57	0.66	0.15	4.48	5.92	1.17
WO-2	Wadu-1	0.66	0.21	2.46	3.14	1.27
<i>Mixed organic matter (Type II ± Type III) :</i>						
SO-1	Sobhasan-66	0.66	0.12	5.14	11.29	2.16
SO-2	Sobhasan-66	0.64	0.13	4.36	8.76	2.05
SO-3	Sobhasan-66	0.65	0.15	3.60	6.76	3.13
SO-4	Sobhasan-66	0.68	0.17	3.25	3.80	3.80
<i>Type II organic matter :</i>						
LY-10	Lynch-3	0.65	0.10	4.37	8.96	2.22
LY-11	Lynch-3	0.63	0.10	5.82	10.78	1.78
LY-12	Lynch-3	0.62	0.10	7.73	13.62	1.84
LY-13	Lynch-3	0.75	0.08	6.93	10.04	1.50
LY-14	Lynch-3	0.89	0.05	4.95	8.38	1.69

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR or G.R. (S.M.) grades unless otherwise stated. A Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer was used for recording the ir spectra.

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